

Southern California CSU DNP Consortium

California State University, Fullerton
California State University, Long Beach
California State University, Los Angeles

IMPROVING NURSING STAFF CONFIDENCE IN PEDIATRIC
CODE BLUE EVENTS

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements

For the degree of

DOCTOR OF NURSING PRACTICE

By

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ABSTRACT

Cardiac arrests in children hospitalized on medical-surgical units are a challenge for pediatric healthcare providers as these events are unanticipated and considered low frequency, high-risk situations requiring precision team work. Staff must also possess the knowledge and skill to respond to patient needs in a timely manner. Once a code blue is initiated, it is essential that staff have confidence in their skills and participate effectively and efficiently in performing any designated nursing role as needed.

Sixty-eight registered nurses from a medical-surgical unit at a tertiary care pediatric hospital participated in a quality improvement project. The purpose of this project was to develop and implement a code blue skills training and practice program for nurses to improve their confidence when performing required skills. Staff attended a skills training session lasting approximately 4 hours and staff had the opportunity to participate in optional surveys before and after the intervention. The Schwarzer General Self-Efficacy Scale (Schwarzer & Jerusalem, 1995) was utilized to evaluate participants' perception of their self-efficacy.

There was a significant increase in nurses' confidence about their code blue skills, and 91% of the nurses reported the intervention was very helpful in offering opportunities to practice code blue related skills. A Wilcoxon Signed-Rank test was used to compare pre- and post-intervention scores and found a statistically significant increase ($p= 0.02$) in the nurses' self-efficacy scores post intervention. This project supported the need to

provide adequate opportunities for staff to practice skills needed in a code blue emergency.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

ABSTRACT.....	iii
LIST OF TABLES.....	vii
LIST OF FIGURES	viii
ACKNOWLEDGMENTS	ix
BACKGROUND	1
Significance	1
Needs Assessment.....	2
Purpose.....	4
Supporting Framework	4
REVIEW OF LITERATURE	8
Overview.....	8
Self-Efficacy	8
Self-Efficacy and the Contribution to Knowledge	9
Educational Strategies to Enhance Self-Efficacy	10
Deliberate Practice	10
Simulation.....	11
Factors Affecting Educational Effectiveness.....	14
Summary.....	15
METHODS	17
Design and Setting.....	17
Participants and Stakeholders	17
Ethical Considerations	19
Measures	19
Intervention.....	20

RESULTS	23
Participant Characteristics	23
Self-Efficacy	23
Confidence Level with Code Blue Skills.....	27
DISCUSSION.....	31
REFERENCES	35
APPENDIX A: PERMISSION TO USE MODEL.....	42
APPENDIX B: LETTER TO STAFF	43
APPENDIX C: LETTER OF SUPPORT.....	44
APPENDIX D: IRB APPROVAL FROM CLINICAL SITE	45
APPENDIX E: IRB APPROVAL FROM CALIFORNIA STATE UNIVERSITY LONG BEACH.....	46
APPENDIX F: PERMISSION TO USE TOOL	47
APPENDIX G: PRE-SURVEY	48
APPENDIX H: POST-SURVEY	50
APPENDIX I: LETTER READ TO STAFF ON DAY OF INTERVENTION	52
APPENDIX J: RESEARCH INFORMATION SHEET	53

LIST OF TABLES

<u>Table</u>	<u>Page</u>
1. Characteristics of Nurses Participating in Code Skills Training and Completion of Pre-and Post- Intervention Surveys	24
2. Comparison of Pre- and Post- Scores on the General Self-Efficacy Scale.....	25
3. Median and IQR for Responses to Survey Items Related to Confidence in Responding to Code Blue Events	27
4. Estimated Regression Coefficients and Corresponding p-values	30

LIST OF FIGURES

<u>Figure</u>	<u>Page</u>
1. Bandura Model	5
2. Distribution of responses from the Generalized Self-Efficacy Scale	26
3. Distribution of responses to the four survey items related to confidence in responding to code blue events	28

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BACKGROUND

Although mortality rates from in-hospital cardiac arrests have decreased and survival rates have improved in the United States, the survival rate for pediatric patients remains low at 36% (American Heart Association, 2016). Seeking to improve pediatric in-hospital survival rates, the American Heart Association set a 50% pediatric survival rate after a cardiac arrest as its 2020 goal (Neumar et al., 2015). Cardiac arrest is defined as “a severe malfunction or cessation of the electrical and mechanical activity of the heart” (Institute of Medicine, 2015, p. 1) and can occur without any warning signs. Cardiac arrests in hospitalized children especially those occurring outside the intensive care area are a challenge for pediatric healthcare providers as these events are considered low frequency, high risk situations requiring precision teamwork which can be difficult if not often experienced. To achieve the 2020 goal, healthcare teams have started to develop interventions and advance systems to improve post arrest patient care outcomes.

Significance

The Institute for Healthcare Improvement (IHI) established the *100,000 Lives Campaign* to develop recommendations for hospitals and healthcare providers to aid in reducing injury and death. One proposal was that hospitals develop and implement Rapid Response Teams (RRTs) to improve quality of patient care and promote patient safety (Institute for Healthcare Improvement, 2015). These teams are comprised of a defined group of healthcare providers who are alerted to quickly respond when a patient’s condition exhibits signs of clinical deterioration. The team arrives within a designated timeframe, assesses the patient, and provides recommendations (Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality, 2017). Rapid Response Teams are present and serve as a highly

functional intervention in many hospitals to improve patient outcomes. An RRT may be initiated by any staff or family member in the hospital who believes there are changes in the patient's condition that warrants additional evaluation. In a systematic review of 29 studies by Maharaj, Raffaele, and Wendon (2015), implementation of a rapid response alert was found to be an effective method of decreasing cardiac arrests in the pediatric population. Additionally, a systematic review by Winters et al. (2013), based on data from seven pediatric hospitals, found implementation of a rapid response system demonstrated significant reduction of nonintensive care unit (ICU) cardiac arrests and mortality in children. In the pediatric population, cardiac arrest is most commonly caused by respiratory failure or shock and nurses need to possess the ability to recognize and respond to a deterioration in the patient's condition (Martin, Keller, Long, & Wenger, 2016).

Needs Assessment

The setting of this DNP project is Children's Hospital Los Angeles (CHLA), a tertiary Magnet-accredited pediatric hospital in Southern California. This facility implemented an RRT call system for its medical-surgical non-ICU units in 2008. Since its implementation, there have been modifications made to improve the efficiency of the RRT such as evaluating who attends an RRT and a review of each event. RRT response rates on the units increased from an average of 423 rapid responses in 2014 to 628 in 2017 (Children's Hospital Los Angeles, 2017). In this organization, when a cardiac or respiratory arrest occurs, a code blue is called. As a result of RRT implementation, the code blue rate on the medical-surgical non-ICU units decreased from an average of 0.40 per month in 2014 to 0.15 per month in 2017 (Children's Hospital Los Angeles, 2017).

An unanticipated outcome from a well-functioning RRT is that nurses reported that they were involved in less code blue events as before and therefore have less comfort in their performance of code blue resuscitation skills.

A 2017 needs assessment on a 32-bed medical unit revealed that nurses were concerned about their ability to function optimally during an arrest situation. While staff are required to renew their Pediatric Advanced Life Support (PALS) and Basic Life Support (BLS) certificates every two years, there are few opportunities to practice code blue skills during actual events. This unit experienced a decrease in code blue situations with an average of 10 arrests in 2017 compared to 12 arrests in 2016 (Children's Hospital Los Angeles, 2017). Currently the organization provides simulated mock codes several times a year. These occur when members of the interprofessional simulation team can schedule them on the various units in the hospital. Nurses working during the shift in which the mock code takes place can participate in the practice event; however, participation may be limited if nurses are busy attending to priority patient care or are not working on the day of the mock code. Staff require opportunities to attend training and emergency skills practice to function competently and confidently in code blue situations. Staff must also possess the knowledge and skill to respond to patient needs in a timely manner. Once a code blue is initiated, it is essential that staff members react and participate effectively and efficiently in performing any designated nursing role as needed. The needs assessment confirmed that staff believed they required additional training in code skills. Evidence shows staff education improves competence and confidence in low frequency events (O' Leary, Nash, & Lewis, 2016). Disher et al. (2014)

reported that active learning is an effective method for learning and performance improvement.

Purpose

This project was initiated by nursing staff on the unit who expressed the desire for specific skills training needed in a code blue event. As a result of this request, the purpose of this project was to develop and implement a code blue skills training and practice program for nurses to improve their confidence when performing required skills.

Supporting Framework

The theoretical framework for this DNP project is Bandura's Social Cognitive Theory. Bandura's theory describes a triad of environmental, personal, and behavioral factors that can shape how the individual behaves in response to challenges such as a patient emergency (Bandura, 2012). His theory identifies several influences which interact in a reciprocal manner. They include action, environmental causative factors, and factors that are self-directed (Bandura, 1989). Individuals can learn to develop methods to deal with challenging events. Those with the ability to handle these challenges become more efficient in their decision making processes (Bandura, 1994).

One component of this theory involves an individual's self-efficacy. Bandura describes self-efficacy as a person's belief in their ability to handle or manage situations, and how much it influences their lives (Bandura, 1994). Self-efficacy beliefs can direct how an individual motivates him or herself when a difficult situation arises. An individual's perceived self-efficacy can affect his or her ability to change and adapt. Bandura notes that self-efficacy can be influenced by cognitive factors, motivation, affective factors, and decision making. Self-efficacy can control behavior directly and

indirectly (Bandura, 2012). Figure 1 describes how self-efficacy can affect an individuals' behavior. This model demonstrates the role of different variables and their effect on behavior.

Figure 1. Bandura Model. Adapted from “On the Functional Properties of Perceived Self-Efficacy Revisited” by Bandura, A. 2012. *Journal of Management*, 38, p.14. See Appendix A for permissions.

Cognitive functioning can be influenced by one's self-efficacy. An individual with strong self-efficacy tends to strive for higher goals and is more motivated to challenge him/herself (Bandura, 1993). Those with high self-efficacy can plan for problems and how they would handle future challenges. Individuals with lower self-efficacy will avoid a situation if they do not feel they have the skill necessary to meet the challenge. Mastery experiences or performance accomplishments strengthen resiliency and self-efficacy. This can occur when the individual perseveres and can perform the task despite obstacles (Bandura, 2012). Self-efficacy can be enhanced through modeling. Social modeling occurs by observing others which can increase ones' belief in his/her

own ability to complete the needed tasks (Bandura, 1994). These vicarious experiences can allow for learning the behavior and improvement of skills. If individuals can observe activities being successfully completed, it may influence how they handle a similar situation in the future should it occur (Bandura, 1989).

When individuals have a strong sense of self-efficacy, they may be more motivated to continue trying to achieve higher goals. If they believe that they have the tools to handle a situation, they are more likely to keep persevering (Bandura, 2012). For individuals to develop high self-efficacy, they need to learn to persevere despite challenges (Bandura, 2012).

An individual's affective process in self-efficacy suggests that one with a strong self-efficacy can handle stressful situations and move on to the next event successfully. Individuals need to learn how they can cope and handle stress when facing difficult and challenging situations. An individual's physiological state is an important part of self-efficacy and affects one's ability to handle stress. (Bandura, 2012). If an individual has good coping skills, it supports self-efficacy (Bandura, 1977). The individual with coping skills can move forward after a difficult situation. For individuals with high self-efficacy, recovery from setbacks is easier and they have the strength to move forward (Bandura, 1989).

Providing sources of information and learning to the individual can also assist in improving goal setting (Bandura, 1994). If individuals only choose goals that are easy to achieve, they may experience frustration when obstacles occur (Bandura, 2012). Goals can be set to motivate and achieve, and meeting the goals can provide the individual with satisfaction (Bandura, 1994). Persuasion is another way to influence self-efficacy. If

individuals can be convinced of their abilities, they are more likely to be successful when challenges arise encouraging self-improvement (Bandura, 2012).

This theory fits well with this DNP project to improve staff confidence in code blue skills for an event not often experienced. Self-efficacy plays a role in the individual's ability to handle difficult situations. A code blue is a challenging situation and having knowledge and the skill set required during such an event will allow staff to develop coping abilities when those situations arise. Staff members may have decreased self-efficacy in their knowledge and competence due to the infrequency of such an event. Staff identifying activities performed during code events as an area they wanted to improve demonstrated their motivation to learn. This project utilized modeling by providing observation and demonstration of skills to improve the staff's cognitive abilities. Staff were asked to perform these skills to develop mastery. Encouragement of the staff can also cause them to feel more self-efficacious. Evaluation of the participants before and after the skills day was used to identify if their perception of self-efficacy in these skills improved.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Overview

A literature review was performed utilizing the following databases: Google Scholar, CINAHL Complete, PubMed, and Web of Science. Databases were accessed through the Pollak Library at California State University, Fullerton and through the Health Science Library at Children's Hospital Los Angeles. A reference librarian was consulted for assistance in this review and development of MeSH terms. The review of literature covered Self-Efficacy, Knowledge, Simulation, Pediatric Patients, Systematic Reviews and Education. MeSH terms included: Nurses, or nurs*, or nursing, confidence* or competence, code blue or cardiac arrest or cardiopulmonary arrest or resuscitat* or cardiopulmonary resuscitat* or cardiopulmonary, infan* or child* or adolescen* or pediatric*, adult, efficacy or self-efficacy, knowledge, attitude, behavior, skills, and educat*. Limits on the search that were used included articles in English and references from peer reviewed journal articles published from 2012 through 2018 only. The reference list in the articles were examined to find additional sources of information. Gray literature was reviewed for information which were judged to be appropriate for this project.

Self-Efficacy

As discussed previously, self-efficacy is a construct in Bandura's Social Learning Theory. It refers to the confidence that one has in performing certain behaviors and in this review the terms "confidence" and "self-efficacy" are used interchangeably. There are four sources that can contribute to improving self-efficacy. They are performance accomplishments, vicarious experiences, verbal persuasion, and physiological states

(Bandura, 2012). The literature review that follows supports incorporating these sources as an aid in influencing self-efficacy. Education and training have been found to be successful in improving an individual's perception of confidence in emergency situations (Roh, Lee, Chung, & Park, 2013). Nurses' lack of confidence in their knowledge and level of skill to handle crisis situations can play a role in their ability to intervene (Crowe, Ewart, & Derman, 2018). Modeling and training can be an effective method to demonstrate a behavior and may improve confidence. The ability to observe, practice, and debrief allows nurses to build self-efficacy (Disher et al., 2014).

Providing training to improve self-efficacy can be beneficial for a variety of professionals working in the healthcare arena. In one study, internationally trained nurses who worked in the United States received simulated training to better manage complex cardiac patients. The confidence that these foreign trained nurses had to care for high-risk patients was improved after training (Tan & Alpert, 2013). Sergeev et al. (2012) found military physicians and paramedics exhibited more self-confidence when performing procedures after they had practiced on mannequins. This simulated experience was associated with a belief of increased self-efficacy when performing the same procedures in different environments. There is a need for a program that allows nurses to actively engage in training experiences which may aid in improving one's confidence about those skills.

Self-Efficacy and the Contribution to Knowledge

Research shows that improving staff knowledge may positively impact self-efficacy. To evaluate an improvement in staff knowledge, Reece, Cooke, Polivka, and Clark (2016) utilized hands on practice along with an educational intervention. Their

findings indicated that nurses perform better following hands on practice versus only reviewing educational materials without any practice. Reece et al. (2016) also found an improvement in confidence levels in those who had participated in the hands on activities. Sankar, Vijayakanthi, Sankar, and Dubey (2013) recruited nursing students and nurses to examine training interventions aimed at improving knowledge. All staff received the same training in pediatric Cardiopulmonary Resuscitation (CPR). Knowledge and confidence improved immediately following training in both groups, however, students retained the knowledge better than nurses. Sankar et al. (2013) attributed this finding to the fact students were able to incorporate this information as part of their educational experience. Additionally, Kurosawa et al. (2014) compared knowledge between two groups of nurses who received different methods of PALS training. One group received several short episodes of training while another group had one full day of training. Skill performance and knowledge were significantly improved and retained in the group receiving shorter sessions though both groups had improved performance. A secondary outcome from this study was that both groups had an improvement in self-reported skill confidence. These findings support that additional knowledge can help improve self-efficacy.

Educational Strategies to Enhance Self-Efficacy

Deliberate Practice

As noted in the review of previous studies, self-efficacy and knowledge can be improved through training. Deliberate practice can be an effective method to provide staff education and improve self-efficacy and competence (Ericsson, 2008). Deliberate practice involves educating through repetition and reinforcement and continued practice

can improve mastery of skills and improve performance (Ericsson, Nandagopal, & Roring, 2009). Ericsson (2008) maintained that deliberate practice should be used to educate, and one should practice until the skill becomes almost instinctive. Deliberate practice can help improve nurses' abilities to perform skills and improve confidence. There have been studies demonstrating that utilization of deliberate practice with nursing students was an effective education modality. Liou, Chang, Tsai, and Cheng (2012), Owen, Garbett, Coburn, and Amar (2017), and Whyte and Cormier (2014) utilized deliberate practice techniques with nursing students and found that repetition improved self-confidence. Knowledge and confidence improved after practicing skills. McDonough et al. (2016) found deliberate practice of skills to be effective in improving nursing staff knowledge and self-efficacy for caring for patients with tracheostomy and laryngectomies. Before the skill session, nurses had a lack of understanding and confidence related to caring for patients with these specific types of patient care needs. By providing a combination of hands on and didactic learning involving deliberate practice, self-efficacy and knowledge increased. This combination of teaching strategies (hands on and didactic learning) was an effective method to educate nurses about specialized care. Studies demonstrated that to maintain confidence in challenging patient situations it is necessary to have regular specific training for staff (Delac, Blazier, Daniel, & N-Wilfong, 2013; Martin, Keller, Long, & Ryan-Wenger, 2016). Deliberate practice can be an effective method to improve skill, knowledge, and self-efficacy.

Simulation

Simulation is an interactive learning environment where scenarios are developed in a realistic situation allowing for enhanced education to practice needed skills. This

type of environment has been found to be safe and conducive to learning (Decker, Sportsman, Puetz, & Billings, 2008). Fidelity in simulation is the level of reality being utilized in training (Clapper et al., 2015). Low fidelity lacks the reality of an actual patient situation, but can be useful for practicing technical skills, while high fidelity provides a three-dimensional realistic patient experience. By understanding the types of simulation, and determining what modality would be most effective, educators can more effectively enhance student learning (Seropian, Brown, Gavilanes, & Driggers, 2004).

Simulated training of students was found to improve knowledge and confidence in skills practiced (Kim, 2018; Merriman, Stayt, & Ricketts, 2014; Treadwell, 2015). Self-efficacy and critical thinking were improved after being exposed to simulation scenarios. Simulated training also provided opportunities for deliberate practice. Studies by Crowe et al. (2018), Disher et al. (2014), O' Leary et al. (2016) and Reece et al. (2016) noted improvement in experienced nurses' self-confidence when they engaged in lecture and simulated scenarios. In addition, Straka, Burkett, Capan, and Eswein (2012) found novice nurses had an increase in perceived self-efficacy about caring for deteriorating patients after participating in mock training. Roh et al. (2013) determined it was valuable to engage nurses in simulated trainings to improve their confidence and decrease anxiety. Simulation was shown to be an effective method to provide nurses and students with education to improve knowledge and self-confidence in emergency situations.

Pediatrics can be a challenging specialty and emergency situations can be difficult if the nurse does not feel confident working with young patients. Strategies were examined which would help improve nurses' recognition of deterioration in pediatric patients. A combination of hands on practice along with classroom training can be an

effective method to disseminate information. After simulated training programs, nurses were more effective in recognition of clinical changes exhibited by the pediatric patient. Additionally, confidence levels increased after training, with nurses believing they could handle a critical situation should one occur (Bultas, Hassler, Ercole, & Rea, 2014; Martin et al., 2016; O' Leary et al., 2016; Sapyta & Eiger, 2017; Straka et al., 2012). This supports the need for education tailored specifically to pediatric nurses' needs as an effective strategy to improve knowledge and confidence.

Onan et al. (2017) performed a systematic review of team-based simulated CPR training with undergraduate students. In a review of 26 studies, they found students who had participated in simulation training either had a similar or higher level of success and knowledge gain in performing CPR resuscitation. Training sessions can provide opportunities for additional practice and improved confidence. Onan et al. also suggested that classes should be organized so there can be a review of performance skills prior to any testing. While this systematic review specifically examined CPR training with students, the information provided can guide others who are educating clinical staff in any training protocol.

It is important to integrate new and creative methods of education to keep the adult learner interested and motivated to learn. Simulation can be the critical link that ties the classroom into practice (Bultas et al., 2014). Roh et al. (2013) found that simulated resuscitation training was important to maintain knowledge as nurses are the first to respond to patient emergencies. Simulation allowed nurses to maintain, develop, and become proficient in their skills. Roh et al. (2013) discussed the need for different modalities of education and supported the need for creative methods.

Factors Affecting Educational Effectiveness

Since healthcare professionals work a variety of shifts in the acute care environment, it is imperative to provide both day and night training opportunities. Martin et al. (2016) noted many novice nurses were assigned to work night shift and addressed the need to schedule training for both day and night shifts. This is especially true if the night staff are more novice and have fewer opportunities to advance their education and skills than do day shift nurses. Education is needed for all nurses as critical changes in a patient's condition may be unpredictable at any time during hospitalization.

Training also needs to allow for staff engagement. Several researchers discussed limitations to their study involving nurses or students having educational sessions conducted while either on the job or after they have been working all day. Delac et al. (2013), Kurosawa et al. (2014), Reece et al. (2016), and Schubert (2012) performed their studies with nurses who were working or received training after having worked a shift. They found these nurses were distracted and anxious and as a result did not focus on their training. Hommes (2014) performed training with newly hired nursing staff during their orientation period, scheduling them to attend the session on a day they were not working on the unit, and found it to be successful. The information from these studies validate the need for dedicated time for staff to receive education where the focus can be on the educational activity rather than staff being distracted about their patient care assignment. It also affirms the need for more research to identify the best time to conduct educational sessions.

The length of training protocols varied throughout the studies examined. Delac et al. (2013), Martin et al. (2016), McDonough et al. (2016), Merriman et al. (2014), Sapyta

and Eiger (2017), and Treadwell (2015) provided training over different amounts of time with successful outcomes. Some studies performed interventions in as short as ten minutes and others were completed over several hours. There were also longitudinal studies which provided training over longer periods of time. Onan et al. (2017) discussed that time was needed for education and practice while Connell et al. (2016) noted brief education sessions could be effective. This is a reminder that training needs to be tailored to what is best for the organization as well as the availability of resources.

Connell et al. (2016) performed a systematic review and examined effectiveness of different types of education in recognizing the decompensating patient and outcome measures used to evaluate effectiveness. They analyzed 23 eligible studies and found simulation in conjunction with other modalities such as didactics to be an effective educational tool that supported knowledge and retention of learning over time. They also concluded that when simulation was blended with these other types of educational methods it was more effective. McDonough et al. (2016), Merriman et al. (2014), and Roh et al. (2013) successfully utilized a combination of educational methods to effectively engage staff.

Summary

This review of literature illustrated the need for a variety of training methods for nurses to improve their perceptions of self-efficacy especially related to preparing them to function effectively when patient emergencies occur. Deliberate practice and simulation education can be used to aid in this process. Providing staff adequate time to participate in training sessions to gain the essential knowledge and skills in a safe and supportive environment is a key factor in supporting staff education and training. The

need to train staff who work on both shifts was highlighted in the review. Patient deterioration especially in the pediatric population can be unpredictable, and provision of educational opportunities for staff to safely handle emergency situations is imperative.

METHODS

This section examines the methods that were used to execute this project. The design, setting, sample, participants and stakeholders as well as ethical considerations are discussed. The measures for this project are reviewed as well as the process for its implementation and evaluation. The purpose of this Quality Improvement (QI) project was to develop and implement a code blue skills training program for nurses to improve self-efficacy.

Design and Setting

This was a QI project involving an educational intervention consisting of three parts: pre-test, staff education and post-test. The setting of this project was Children's Hospital Los Angeles (CHLA), a Southern California 390 bed pediatric Magnet hospital. The hospital serves pediatric patients from birth to adults up to twenty-one years of age. It has the following inpatient units: Heart Center, Pediatric Intensive Care, Neonatal Intensive Care, Hematology/Oncology and Medical-surgical units. The nursing unit that was the focus of this QI project is a 32-bed medical-surgical unit. Patient diagnoses on this unit include pulmonary, neurology, and general pediatric illnesses. This unit also receives step down patients from the ICUs. The age range on this unit includes patients a few days old to adults up to twenty-one years of age. The educational intervention took place in education classrooms located within the organization. There were several classrooms used for this intervention.

Participants and Stakeholders

This project included registered nurses (RNs) employed at CHLA and employed on a 32-bed medical-surgical inpatient unit. There were approximately 80 nurses on this

unit. Staff ranged in nursing experience from several months to over 30 years of experience. Staff were full or part time with a few per diem staff employees. The staff were employed by the hospital and there were no registry or contracted employees. The nurses had associate, baccalaureate, or master's degrees. The unit had recently been receiving patients with higher acuities necessitating the need to hire more experienced nurses who were new to the organization.

All of the nurses were informed of the skills training via email, the standard method of notification of education offerings. Two classes were available for the training and staff were to attend one of the two dates. Staff were provided the intervention on two different dates: October 8, 2018 and November 5, 2018 from 7:30 am until 11:30 am.

As per the nurses' normal scheduling practice, staff determined the date they would participate in the class. The educational intervention was mandatory, but participation in the surveys was optional. A flyer was developed and posted in the staff breakroom approximately two months before the intervention to inform staff about the class and the ability to participate in a survey about their level of confidence (Appendix B).

The stakeholders for this project included: the Nursing Director of Rehabilitation and Medical Services, the Operations Manager for the unit, and the Clinical Educator for the unit. They were informed of the project and were supportive of the need for this plan. Meetings were held periodically to keep them up to date with the project and solicit their input. They continued to provide support and reinforce the need for this type of staff education as well as reviewing the surveys.

Ethical Considerations

The organization provided a letter of support (Appendix C). Institutional Review Board (IRB) approval was obtained from the organization (Appendix D) and also at California State University Long Beach (Appendix E). The project did not involve patients so there was no risk to patients. There was minimal risk to staff related to confidentiality and concerns about evaluation of performance in the skills training program. Anxiety can increase when staff know they are being evaluated, thus affecting performance. Interventions were in place to protect staff identity on the surveys. Staff selected a personal identifier known only to them (Appendix I). There was no testing of skills during the training and this was relayed to staff at the start of the intervention. Staff were instructed there would be no negative consequences should they choose not to participate in the pre/posttest.

Measures

Self-efficacy, the confidence one has in the ability to perform a skill (Bandura, 2012), was the specific construct that was measured. The Schwarzer General Self-Efficacy Scale, a paper and pencil tool, was used to elicit participant information about this concept. This tool consists of ten items with a scoring range from one to four. An individual's scale score is determined by finding the sum of all items. The score ranges are between 10 and 40 and a higher score indicates a belief of one's increased self-efficacy (Schwarzer & Jerusalem, 1995). Permission to use the tool can be found in Appendix F. Reliability of this tool was tested with samples from 23 nations and the scale was found to be unidimensional with a Cronbach's alpha in the mid 80's (Schwarzer &

Jerusalem, 1995). Criterion-related validity for this tool was documented in other correlational studies (Schwarzer & Jerusalem, 1995).

Additional questions were added for participants to respond to that focused on certain tasks related to confidence in arrest situations. Prior to the use of this modified tool, unit educators and managers were asked to review the tool. The tool was administered to four RNs not employed on the unit of study to determine test-retest reliability. The four nursing staff answered the survey questions at a 90% agreement when administered at two different times approximately one month apart. The pre-survey included demographic data and questions related to prior experiences in code blue while the post-survey included questions related to course evaluation. Appendix G includes the pre-survey and Appendix H includes the post-survey.

Intervention

After IRB approval was granted, RNs from the unit attended one of two educational sessions in October and November 2018 in classrooms located in the hospital. They were preassigned to a session by the unit scheduler which was the standard process used in scheduling any education for staff on the project unit. They received an email with the time and location of the intervention one week prior to the date they were to attend. On the day of the intervention, once all staff arrived, they were informed of the purpose of the project and were told they would all receive the training with the option to participate in the project (i.e., completing the assessment tools). Standardized information in the form of a written script was provided and read by the instructors (Appendix I) before the start of each session. Staff were also informed this educational session did not include testing as staff can become anxious when skills are tested. Prior to the

intervention at each session, all participants were given an informed consent by one of the instructors. See Appendix J for consent. All participants were given a pre-survey which was placed in a box. Those choosing not to participate submitted a blank survey.

The intervention involved four different skill stations. Rotation of stations were assigned on the day of intervention based on number of nurses in attendance. After consultation with the research director in the organization it was decided to place nurses in groups based on level of experience. By doing this, it allowed those with similar skill levels to work together in the groups. The nurses rotated to a new station hourly. Instructors for stations were certified PALS instructors.

The first station involved a crash cart review. The crash carts are standardized and not often opened, so staff may not be familiar with the contents. The instructor reviewed contents of each drawer and staff participated in a relay game to gather supplies needed for three common emergency procedures. These procedures included: intubation, insertion of a nasogastric tube or oral airway, and insertion of a peripheral intravenous catheter. Station two focused on code medications. Medication administration is typically a challenge for many nurses in pediatrics as many medications need to be drawn from their medication injector and often small doses are needed. A review of drawing up medications using a needle-less system and stopcock was done. All staff were observed drawing up three different doses of medication. Station three involved a practice session utilizing the push-pull method for drawing up a fluid bolus. In a code, nurses are often called upon to provide a bolus in this manner. The instructor reviewed the process then observed all staff demonstrating administration of a bolus. All staff were able to practice this skill twice. Station four was a defibrillation review station. The instructor reviewed

how to apply pads, turn on the machine, determine joules setting, and the process for defibrillation and cardioversion based on PALS guidelines. There were different types of heart rhythms for staff to identify for defibrillation or cardioversion. Staff performed return demonstrations for at least one arrhythmia. After completion of the fourth skill station, a post survey was administered in the same room. Staff were asked to put the survey (completed or not completed) into a labeled box. Surveys were collected by one of the instructors and placed in the project director's locked office.

RESULTS

The results of this project were aimed at determining whether the educational intervention was effective in improving staff confidence about their level of competence to function effectively during pediatric code blue events

Participant Characteristics

A total of 68 registered nurses participated in the educational offering with 67 of them completing both a pre and post survey. This QI project revealed that 92% of nurses found the intervention very helpful in providing an overview of how to manage code blue events. Similarly, 91% found it very helpful in offering opportunities to practice code blue related skills and 86% found it very helpful in gaining experience in handling code blue events. Table 1 summarizes the characteristics of the staff who attended. Over 71% of those who attended had 10 years or less of nursing experience. Both day and night shift were equally represented in the results of the intervention. The majority of nurses were Bachelor of Science (BSN) prepared. Prior participation in mock code trainings and in code blue situations were also very similar (0.82 and 0.97). There was equal distribution between nurses who took PALS at the hospital and those who took it outside the organization. Of note, 61.2% of the staff had their last PALS training at least ten months prior to the intervention.

General Self-Efficacy

The Generalized Self-Efficacy Scale (Schwarzer & Jerusalem, 1999) was completed by the participants prior to the intervention and immediately after completion of the four stations. This scale has ten questions and uses a 4-point scale where 1= “Not at all true”, 2= “Hardly true”, 3= “Moderately true” and 4= “Exactly true.” A total score

was calculated by adding the participants' responses across the ten items. Total potential scores range from 10-40. This scale is not specific for the healthcare setting; however, participants completed the scale as part of a survey related to their response to code blue events. Therefore, it was assumed that they would have interpreted questions as being related to those skills.

Table 1

Characteristics of Nurses Participating in Code Skills Training and Completion of Pre- and Post-Intervention Surveys

		N (%) Mean ± SD
RN Experience (years)	0-5	33 (49.3)
	6-10	15 (22.4)
	11-15	5 (7.5)
	16-20	4 (6.0)
	>20	10 (14.9)
Shift	Day	32 (47.8)
	Night	35 (52.2)
Highest Level of Education	Associate Degree	5 (7.5)
	Bachelor's Degree	58 (86.6)
	Master's Degree	4 (6.0)
Participation in mock code trainings during previous year		0.82 ± 0.76
Participation in code blue/cardiac arrest events during the previous year		0.97 ± 1.16
Last PALS training	1-3 months ago	11 (16.4)
	4-6 months ago	7 (10.4)
	7-10 months ago	8 (11.9)
	10-12 months ago	16 (23.9)
	Over a year ago	25 (37.3)
PALS taken at CHLA	Yes	34 (50.7)
	No	33 (49.3)

Staff were also informed prior to participation that the purpose of the educational session was to evaluate if this method of education was effective to help staff improve self-confidence. This also allowed participants to complete the Generalized Self-Efficacy Scale in relation to code blue events. Of the 67 respondents, 38 had an increase in their self-efficacy score post intervention, 21 had no change in their post self-efficacy score while eight respondents had a decrease in their post self-efficacy score. Table 2 shows the median and interquartile range (IQR) of total scores before and after the intervention. A Wilcoxon Signed-Rank test was used to test for a significant difference in the pre and post scores. A statistically significant p -value of 0.02 was found post intervention.

Table 2

Comparison of Pre- and Post-Intervention Scores on the Generalized Self-Efficacy Scale

General Self-Efficacy Scale	Pre-Intervention	Post-Intervention	p -value
	Median (IQR)	Median (IQR)	
Total Score	30.0 (3.0)	32.0 (5.0)	0.02

Figure 2 shows the distribution of the responses for each item of the General Self-Efficacy. Post-Intervention responses demonstrate changes in self-efficacy especially for the questions, “I am confident that I could deal efficiently with unexpected events” and “If someone opposes me, I can find the means and ways to get what I want.” If the participants were evaluating their self-efficacy regarding code blue events, this may demonstrate the intervention could have provided them tools to be successful. In general, all self-efficacy scores improved post intervention.

Figure 2. Distribution of Responses to the Generalized Self-Efficacy Scale.

Confidence Level with Code Blue Skills

Participants responded to four survey items intended to assess their confidence in skills related to code blue events. These items were scored on a 3-point scale where a score of 1 indicates “Not Confident”, 2 indicates “Somewhat Confident”, and 3 indicates “Confident”. A median and interquartile range (IQR) is reported for each item (Table 3). Figure 3 depicts the distribution of responses to the 4 items in the pre- and post-intervention surveys. A median was used because it is hard to say what the average between the different levels of confidence may be. The median still provides an idea of an “average” response without making assumptions about the data. The frequency of each response demonstrates that participants were much more confident in their skills after the intervention.

Table 3

Median and IQR for Responses to Survey Items Related to Confidence in Responding to Code Blue Events

	Pre-Survey	Post-Survey
	Median (IQR)	Median (IQR)
1. I can prepare ordered medications accurately	2 (0.5)	3 (1)
2. I can find the requested items needed from the crash cart	2 (1)	3 (0)
3. I can quickly prepare for defibrillation	2 (1)	3 (0)
4. I can efficiently use the push/pull method for administering a fluid bolus	2 (1)	3 (0)

Figure 3. Distribution of responses to the four survey items related to confidence in responding to code blue events.

The effect of the educational intervention on confidence level was examined using an ordinal regression model with R programming language (R Core Team, 2014). Each of the four survey items in Table 3 were modeled separately with the response to each survey item acting as a dependent variable. A ‘time’ variable was used as a covariate to test for a difference between pre- and post-intervention responses. Other demographic information was included as covariates except for education as approximately 87% of the respondents had the same highest education level (BSN). In all four models, there was a significant, positive association with the survey response (i.e., the participant reported greater confidence on the post-intervention survey relative to the pre-survey) for each intervention (Table 4). Regarding model 4, the number of code blue events experienced in the previous year was significantly and positively associated with the response, demonstrating that nurses with more experience responding to code blue events reported increased confidence using the push/pull method to administer a fluid

bolus. In this same model, staff with 11-15 years of RN experience had a significant, positive associations with the response. There were only five RNs in this group which could be a factor as to why a significant association was found. While years of experience was not a significant predictor, the results demonstrate that there was a significant increase in confidence across all years of experience.

Summary of Results

The results of this quality improvement project demonstrated the success of the intervention in improving staff confidence with skills needed during code blue events. Bandura's theory served as foundation for this project. Allowing staff to observe and demonstrate gave them an increased confidence in skills not often utilized. Verbal feedback from nurses after the class included: "Great class", "really helpful", and "this class provided me a lot of good information and practice". In a recent pediatric emergency, one staff member commented to this author, "I remembered what I learned in the class and it was helpful with this patient. I was able to do the fluid bolus with smaller syringes and it went better" Providing staff the opportunity to focus on the education and use deliberate practice with skills allowed them to improve their self-confidence with the identified skills.

Table 4

Estimated Regression Coefficients and Corresponding P-Values

		Model 1		Model 2		Model 3		Model 4	
Survey Item/Response Variable		<i>I can prepare ordered medications accurately</i>		<i>I can find the requested items needed from the crash cart</i>		<i>I can quickly prepare for defibrillation</i>		<i>I can efficiently use the push/pull method for administering a fluid bolus</i>	
Covariate	Level	Estimated Coefficient	p-value	Estimated Coefficient	p-value	Estimated Coefficient	p-value	Estimated Coefficient	p-value
Time	Pre-Intervention					<i>Reference Level</i>			
	Post-Intervention	3.21	7.39 x10⁻⁴	4.39	1.31 x10⁻⁸	5.71	1.57 x10⁻⁵	4.54	1.7 x10⁻⁶
Shift	Day					<i>Reference Level</i>			
	Night	0.06	0.94	0.85	0.14	1.31	0.15	-0.11	0.86
Number of Code Blue events in previous year	--	0.23	0.51	0.21	0.40	0.04	0.90	0.84	0.02
Number of mock codes in previous year	--	0.34	0.45	-0.18	0.55	0.15	0.74	0.16	0.64
Was last PALS taken at CHLA	No					<i>Reference Level</i>			
	Yes	-1.23	0.13	-0.60	0.25	-0.63	0.44	-0.11	0.85
When was last PALS training completed	1-3 months					<i>Reference Level</i>			
	4-6 months	2.86	0.06	0.46	0.62	0.01	1.00	1.55	0.17
	7-10 months	-1.74	0.19	0.85	0.34	-0.49	0.73	1.00	0.35
	10-12 months	-1.08	0.38	1.17	0.18	0.11	0.94	0.41	0.68
	>1 year	-0.95	0.38	1.11	0.14	0.06	0.96	0.59	0.49
RN Experience	0-5					<i>Reference Level</i>			
	6-10	0.65	0.45	0.96	0.11	-0.29	0.75	0.65	0.34
	11-15	2.84	0.05	1.93	0.06	1.02	0.45	3.08	0.02
	16-20	0.77	0.61	0.44	0.69	0.89	0.58	-0.53	0.66
	>20	1.27	0.26	0.41	0.59	-0.28	0.81	1.90	0.05

DISCUSSION

The skills course designed for this project provided nurses the opportunity to observe and practice skills not often used which supports Bandura's theory and is consistent with findings noted in the review of literature. Connell et al. (2016) found simulation activities to be effective for improving technique and skills used in managing a deteriorating patient. Sergeev et al. (2012) found self-confidence improved with practice gained on mannequins. Crowe, Ewart & Derman (2018) also found simulated training was effective in improving a nurse's self-confidence when caring for a deteriorating patient.

There were eight participants who had a decrease in the self-efficacy. This could be because they thought they were confident in the skills, but after practicing they may have learned new information affecting their perceived self-efficacy. This also may be related to how they interpreted the questions from the survey.

There were also questions related to nurses' perception of their skills based on previous code blue events and questions related to confidence level with code blue skills. Because both sets of questions were worded using 'I can' statements, rather than 'I have' or 'I did', they may have been interpreted in the same way as the questions related to confidence level with code blue skills. Little additional information was gained by these questions and they were not included in the results.

There were some challenges with room availability. Approximately two months prior to the intervention, the allotted rooms were closed due to construction. Because the rooms were cancelled late in the year, there was limited availability of the necessary space needed for the intervention. Because new dates were arranged, there was an

additional challenge in scheduling all staff to be able to participate and about 15 staff were not able to attend.

A limitation to this project was the scheduling of the post-test immediately after the practice session, which could affect whether there would be long-term retention of information. Providing additional supplemental material may be a way to support retention of what was learned during the class.

Implications for Practice

This intervention demonstrated the importance of developing an educational program based on staff needs regarding their ability to confidently respond to code blue events. By providing this intervention, it was the author's intent that staff would be able to respond better to unexpected events with more confidence. Allowing staff to have adequate time while not working on the floor to reinforce skill development was also highlighted. Reece et al. (2016) reported nurses felt rushed when taken off the unit to complete educational activities. Scheduling of staff for training during work hours was demonstrated to be challenging for staff (Disher et al. 2014). This author believes that scheduling sessions during non-work hours is an important consideration for future educational projects similar to this one. Additionally, the author believes that positive, significant results emerged from this QI project that were based on the research literature which supported not scheduling code blue educational training sessions during work hours and providing staff time to practice key skills without testing.

Lastly, providing the intervention in a safe and therapeutic manner, not testing participants if possible, and allowing for questions all provided staff the opportunity to be comfortable in their environment and enhanced their experience. At a recent mock code

practice event for physicians several nurses participated in the event. They verbalized to the project leader that the information they received during the training was helpful during the mock code practice. Shortly after training, staff had an opportunity to use skills learned during the class. The staff members responding to a patient emergency reported to the author that they were able to find equipment quickly and efficiently.

Future Considerations

This intervention was successful in improving nurses' self-confidence with specific skills utilized in code blue events. Future consideration should include how often this type of education should be repeated. While the participants rotated through stations hourly, shorter, refresher sessions could possibly be implemented since the nurses had participated in the initial education.

The survey was provided with no specific direction about whether to consider the General Self-Efficacy scale in relation to code blue/cardiac arrests or their general feelings. This should be clarified if using this tool for future similar interventions.

The opportunity to run mock codes approximately 3-4 months after the education and look for improvement in the four skill sets would be one method to determine whether the intervention effect was sustained. The ability to debrief with staff after an actual code blue to determine if the skills education received was helpful to them would also be a method of post-education evaluation.

There are PALS videos available with different teaching scenarios. Future plans at CHLA include evaluating these videos for staff to use. Posting them on the units' SharePoint site or developing unit specific videos could potentially provide knowledge sharing among the nurses and allow more opportunities to practice. Embedded in these

videos would be interactive scenarios built-in to reinforce what was taught. This will provide additional opportunities for staff to gain more exposure and enhance their self-efficacy.

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APPENDIX A

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APPENDIX B
INFORMATIONAL FLYER

Children's Hospital Los Angeles Evidence-Based Research Study
Improving Nursing Staff Confidence during Pediatric Code Blue Events

Principal Investigator: Ruth Paul MSN, RN-BC
323-361-5391
rpaul@chla.usc.edu

Purpose: To determine if a code blue skills educational session will improve nurses' confidence in an emergency situation.

Eligibility Criteria: All 5East RNs are eligible to participate in this project.

Procedures: Completion of a short survey before and after the 4-hour educational session.
The surveys will take approximately 5-10 minutes to complete and will be administered on paper.

Participation is voluntary. Regardless of if you participate in the surveys, you will still receive education.

APPENDIX C**LETTER OF SUPPORT**

April 23, 2018

To Whom It May Concern:

This letter acknowledges my support of Ruth Paul's DNP project and its implementation at Children's Hospital Los Angeles. I am aware she is doing a Quality Improvement (QI) project that involves an educational intervention. The purpose of this QI project is to implement a pediatric code blue training session and evaluate its impact on the staff's confidence level. A pre-and post-survey will be used to measure staff perception of their ability to function effectively during actual code blue events. Ms. Paul will submit her project to the organization's IRB for approval prior to implementation. I do not foresee any impediments to her project.

Sincerely,

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read "Sharon Chinn".

Sharon Chinn RN, CRRN
Director, Clinical Services

APPENDIX D

IRB APPROVAL FROM CLINICAL SITE

Jun 13, 2018, 12:57pm

To: [Ruth Paul, MSN, RN](#)
CLINICAL SERVICES - CHLA

From: Rita Secola, PhD, RN, CPON
Chair Designee, Children's Hospital Los Angeles
Institutional Review Board

Re: CHLA-18-00261 [Ruth Paul, MSN, RN](#)
Improving Nursing Staff Confidence during Pediatric
Code Blue Events ([Staff Confidence](#))

NOTICE OF IRB EXEMPTION

Review Date: 6/13/2018

Document(s) Reviewed:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • iStar Application (dated 6/11/2018) • Research Information Sheet (dated 6/7/2018)
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The above-named study was reviewed by a member of the CHLA IRB. The study has been granted an exemption per 45 CFR 46.101[b][1] and [2].

Please note that this exemption is granted on the basis of the submission describing the research. Any changes or modifications to the study will require submission of an amendment application in order to complete the standard iStar application for research subject to regulation. If the changes to the protocol result in a change of review status to expedited or full Board review, standard continuing IRB review of the protocol will be required.

Children's Hospital Los Angeles is committed to protecting the rights and welfare of human research subjects in all human research which is: 1) sponsored by CHLA; 2) performed by CHLA faculty or staff; 3) performed using CHLA facilities; and/or 4) performed using CHLA patients or nonpublic information about CHLA patients. The IRB is organized and operates according to Federal regulations (45 CFR 46 and 21 CFR 56) and ethical principles. CHLA has negotiated a Federal-Wide Assurance (00001914) with the Office for Human Research Protections and operates according to California regulations.

APPENDIX E**IRB APPROVAL CALIFORNIA STATE UNIVERSITY LONG BEACH****CALIFORNIA STATE UNIVERSITY, LONG BEACH****OFFICE OF RESEARCH & SPONSORED PROGRAMS**

DATE: July 10, 2018

TO: Ruth Paul, MSN, RN-BC

FROM: CSULB IRB

PROJECT TITLE: [1280723-2] Improving nursing staff confidence during pediatric code blue events

REFERENCE #: 18-452

SUBMISSION TYPE: New Project

ACTION: DETERMINATION OF NOT RESEARCH

DECISION DATE: July 10, 2018

Thank you for your submission of New Project materials for this project. The California State University, Long Beach Institutional Review Board has determined this project does not meet the definition of human subject research according to the Department of Health and Human Services (HHS) regulation at 45 CFR 46.101. This project includes a nursing staff educational intervention to improve system functions on the nursing unit. The information gathered does not contribute to generalizable knowledge.

We will retain a copy of this correspondence within our records.

If you have any questions, please contact Mary Walker at (562) 985-8147 or IRB@csulb.edu. Please include your project title and reference number in all correspondence with this committee.

This letter has been electronically signed in accordance with all applicable regulations, and a copy is retained within California State University, Long Beach Institutional Review Board's records.

APPENDIX F

PERMISSION TO USE TOOL

Freie Universität Berlin, Gesundheitspsychologie (PF 10),
Habelschwerdter Allee 45, 14195 Berlin, Germany

Fachbereich Erziehungs-
wissenschaft und Psychologie
- Gesundheitspsychologie -
Professor Dr. Ralf Schwarzer
Habelschwerdter Allee 45
14195 Berlin, Germany

Fax +49 30 838 55634
health@zedat.fu-berlin.de
www.fu-berlin.de/gesund

Permission granted

to use the General Self-Efficacy Scale for non-commercial research and development purposes. The scale may be shortened and/or modified to meet the particular requirements of the research context.

<http://userpage.fu-berlin.de/~health/selfscal.htm>

You may print an unlimited number of copies on paper for distribution to research participants. Or the scale may be used in online survey research if the user group is limited to certified users who enter the website with a password.

There is no permission to publish the scale in the Internet, or to print it in publications (except 1 sample item).

The source needs to be cited, the URL mentioned above as well as the book publication:

Schwarzer, R., & Jerusalem, M. (1995). Generalized Self-Efficacy scale. In J. Weinman, S. Wright, & M. Johnston, *Measures in health psychology: A user's portfolio. Causal and control beliefs* (pp.35-37). Windsor, UK: NFER-NELSON.

Professor Dr. Ralf Schwarzer
www.ralfschwarzer.de

APPENDIX G

PRE-SURVEY

Participant ID (make, model and year of first car): _____

How many years have you worked as an RN

<5

6-10

11-15

16-20

>20 years

What shift do you primarily work?

Day Shift

Night Shift

How many code blue/cardiac arrests have you participated in during the past year?

Please answer the following questions using the scale to the right of the question.

	Not at all True	Hardly True	Moderately True	Exactly True
I can always manage to solve difficult problems if I try hard enough				
If someone opposes me, I can find the means and ways to get what I want				
It is easy for me to stick to my aims and accomplish my goals				
I am confident that I could deal efficiently with unexpected events				
Thanks to my resourcefulness, I know how to handle unforeseen situations				
I can solve most problems if I invest the necessary effort				
I can remain calm when facing difficulties because I can rely on my coping abilities				
When I am confronted with a problem, I can usually find several solutions				

If I am in trouble, I can usually think of a solution				
I can usually handle whatever comes my way				

Schwarzer, R., & Jerusalem, M. (1995). Generalized self-efficacy scale. In J. Weinman, S. Wright, & M. Johnston, *Measures in health psychology: A user's portfolio. Causal and control beliefs* (pp. 35-57). Windsor, UK: NFER-NELSON

Based on your prior experience in Code Blue events, please answer the following questions using the scale below

1= Some of the time 2 = Most of the time 3 = All of the time

When I receive an order for a code medication, I can quickly draw up the correct dose _____

I can set up defibrillation quickly during a code blue _____

If defibrillation is ordered, I am able to promptly program the required joules _____

If a fluid bolus is ordered for a patient, I can administer it using the push/pull method _____

If I am asked to find an item in the crash cart, I can efficiently retrieve that item _____

Please rate your confidence level during a code blue using the scale below for the following skills

1 = Not Confident 2 = Somewhat Confident 3 = Confident

I can prepare ordered medications accurately _____

I can find the requested items needed from the crash cart _____

I can quickly prepare for defibrillation _____

I can efficiently use the push/pull method for administering a fluid bolus _____

APPENDIX H
POST-SURVEY

Participant ID: (make model and year of first car) _____

Please answer the following questions using the scale to the right of the question

	Not at all True	Hardly True	Moderately True	Exactly True
I can always manage to solve difficult problems if I try hard enough				
If someone opposes me, I can find the means and ways to get what I want				
It is easy for me to stick to my aims and accomplish my goals				
I am confident that I could deal efficiently with unexpected events				
Thanks to my resourcefulness, I know how to handle unforeseen situations				
I can solve most problems if I invest the necessary effort				
I can remain calm when facing difficulties because I can rely on my coping abilities				
When I am confronted with a problem, I can usually find several solutions				
If I am in trouble, I can usually think of a solution				
I can usually handle whatever comes my way				

Schwarzer, R., & Jerusalem, M. (1995). Generalized self-efficacy scale. In J. Weinman, S. Wright, & M. Johnston, *Measures in health psychology: A user's portfolio. Causal and control beliefs* (pp. 35-57). Windsor, UK: NFER-NELSON

Please rate the following questions using the scale below

1 = Not Helpful 2= Somewhat Helpful 3 = Very Helpful

To what extent was the course helpful in accomplishing the following tasks

Providing an overview of how to manage code blue events _____

Offering opportunities to practice code blue related skills _____

Gaining experience in handling code blue events _____

Please rate your confidence level during a code blue using the scale below for the following skills

1 = Not Confident 2 = Somewhat Confident 3 = Confident

I can prepare ordered medications accurately _____

I can find the requested items needed from the crash cart _____

I can quickly prepare for defibrillation _____

I can efficiently use the push/pull method for administering a fluid bolus

APPENDIX I**LETTER READ TO STAFF DAY OF INTERVENTION**

Good Morning

Thank you for coming. As you are aware, Ruth Paul is in the process of completing her Doctorate of Nursing Practice, or DNP. Her DNP project is evaluating whether this type of education is an effective method to teach staff to help improve self-confidence during code blue patient events.

As part of her project, she is asking if staff would be interested in completing a short survey before and after the 4 skills. I'm going to hand out an information sheet and a survey to everyone, but participation in the survey is completely option and takes about 5 minutes to complete.

If you choose to participate, please select a participant ID you will remember to use again for the survey at the end of the class. Please use the make/model/year of your first car.

If you do not choose to participate in the survey, just place the blank survey in the envelope.

Thanks for your help

APPENDIX J

RESEARCH INFORMATION SHEET

Children's Hospital Los Angeles
RESEARCH INFORMATION SHEET
Improving Nursing Staff Confidence during Pediatric Code Blue Events

You are invited to participate in an evidence-based research study conducted by Ruth Paul MSN, RN-BC from 5 East at Children's Hospital Los Angeles (CHLA) and a DNP student at California State University. Participation in this study is completely voluntary.

The purpose of the study is to determine if a code blue skills educational session will improve nurses' confidence in an emergency situation. If you volunteer to participate in this study, your participation will involve completion of a short anonymous survey before and after a 4-hour educational session. The surveys will take approximately 5-10 minutes to complete and will be administered on paper.

This study involves the potential risk of accidental release of confidential information. To link the surveys, you will select a Participant ID known only to you, and no attempts will be made to identify you. You should not expect any direct benefit as a result of participating in this research, but we hope to determine if this technique is an effective method to review information with nursing staff. The alternative to participation is to not participate, but regardless of if you participate in the surveys, you will still receive education.

There are not costs related to participation, and you will not be compensated for participating in this study.

Only the research team will know that you are a research subject and have access to the information you provide. None of the information will be disclosed to others; except if necessary to protect your rights or welfare or if required by law (i.e., harm to self or others, reports of certain infectious diseases). You will not be identified in publications of the research results. Authorized representatives of the CHLA Institutional Review Board may review subject records but are bound by rules of confidentiality not to reveal your identity.

Your choice about whether or not to participate will have no effect on your employment, position, or evaluation at Children's Hospital Los Angeles. If you agree to participate, but later decide to withdraw from this study, you may do so without affecting your employment, position, or evaluation at CHLA.

If you have questions about the research or wish to report a concern or complaint about the research, the Principal Investigator, Ruth Paul may be reached at (323) 361-5391. You may withdraw from this study at any time and discontinue participation without penalty. You are not waiving any legal claims, rights or remedies because of your participation in this research study. If you have questions regarding the rights of research subjects or if you have complaints or concerns about the research and cannot reach the Principal Investigator; or just want to talk to someone other than the Investigator, you may call the CHLA Human Subjects Protection Program at (323) 361-2265.